

Towards Runtime-Clustering and improved Implementations of collective Operations in MPI

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Abstract

Further performance improvements of parallel simulation applications will not be reached by simply scaling today's simulation algorithms and system software. Rather, they need qualitatively different approaches and new developments that address and reduce the typically non-linearly increasing complexity of algorithms with the use of increasing processor counts. We presented first results of an activity aimed at improving the performance of collective communication operations of relevance to simulation applications through more efficient implementations of collective communication operations for large-scale program executions.

I. INTRODUCTION

Further performance improvements of parallel simulation applications will not be reached by simply scaling today's simulation algorithms and system software. Rather, they need qualitatively different approaches and new developments that address and reduce the typically non-linearly increasing complexity of algorithms with the use of increasing processor counts.

We present in this paper first results of an activity aimed at improving the performance of collective communication operations of relevance to simulation applications. We focus here on further improvement of applications through more efficient implementations of collective communication operations for large-scale program executions. The development begun in the EU FP7 projects PRACE-IIP and CRESTA and will now be continued in PRACE-2IP with further developments, benchmarks on PRACE systems and application of the result in community codes.

We follow two related lines in the development. One line is to use algorithms based on point-to-point communication operations as the starting point for a topology-optimised implementation using recently established capabilities of multi- and many-core processors as well as interconnect technology. Another line aims at improved use of memory hierarchies that influence the performance of communication operations significantly. Both directions need knowledge about the topology of the computer system that executes the application. An approach and a tool to detect the topology of a HPC computer system is therefore an important part of any solution. One such possible approach has been developed in our development effort.

Many present day supercomputers have multiple level of interconnect bandwidth and latency between processing cores. Message bandwidth and latency between processes running on cores within same numa-zone is generally best, followed by cores in the same node, cores connected by same switch, cores connected by higher level switches etc. The message bandwidth and latency hierarchy can have impact on the performance of MPI jobs. Normally, MPI programs do not distinguish between ranks in the same node and ranks across different nodes. This may lead to over- or under-utilization of interconnects respectively. In the case of MPI collective operations it is however possible to optimally use the network bandwidth by carefully writing the collective algorithm. In PRACE-IIP we developed a routine called `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned`, which does all-to-all (vector) operation utilizing bandwidth and latency hierarchy. This routine was tried in the PRACE euroben synthetic benchmark routine called `mod2f`. The `mod2f` calculates a fast Fourier transform (fft). The standard implementation uses `MPI_Alltoallv` to take the transpose of a matrix. In the modified implementation `MPI_Alltoallv` is replaced with `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned`. The performance and scaling of the modified `mod2f` is greatly improved. In the current work we continue to extend this work. We try to improve the `MPI_Alltoallv_tuned` interface and we want to try it for more realistic applications.

The results will directly be beneficial to applications as well as be used as a building block in a runtime-system aiming at improving application load balance dynamically.

II. RELATED WORK

Efficient algorithms for collective communications have been developed during long-term research [3]. The prevailing use of multi-core processors and progress in network technology has made new communication algorithms and topology-

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awareness in the routing of messages necessary [4,6]. There are some efforts in recent times to make MPI programs topology aware [10, 11, 12]. The library ADCL (Abstract Data and Communication Library) provides communication operations that complement those provided by the MPI standard and selects one algorithm at runtime [2].

Previous work in the area of network topology identification includes the very interesting recent publication by Subramoni et al. [16, 17]. Where a neighbour joining algorithm was employed to identify network topology. The neighbour joining algorithm is a variant of the hierarchical clustering methods and the results presented by Subramoni et al. provide encouraging evidence that the statistical approach is viable.

III. DEVELOPMENT ACTIVITIES

A. Topology-aware all-to-all communication

1) Description

The MPI_Alltoallv_tuned that was developed earlier does the same operation as MPI_Alltoallv but it utilizes the intra node bandwidth more efficiently. It distinguishes between ranks in the same node and ranks across different nodes. In all-to-all operation each rank sends/receives data to/from all ranks. In MPI_Alltoallv_tuned each rank first sends together total data meant for all ranks in each node to only one partner rank in each node. After this stage all the nodes have the full data, however, the rank wise distribution of data is in an intermediate stage. In the 2nd stage this intermediate data is redistributed within the node to put it in the right place w.r.t to individual ranks. The 1st stage is message passing across nodes over a smaller number of ranks. The 2nd stage is entirely within each node. A more detailed description of the algorithm and results is given in [8].

The interface of MPI_Alltoallv_tuned in the earlier implementation was:

```
int MPI_Alltoallv_tuned(double *bufin, ptarr gr_scnt, ptarr gr_sdpl, double *,
                      ptarr gr_rcnt, ptarr gr_rdpl, gcom comm);
```

where *ptarr* and *gcom* have the following data types

```
typedef struct {int *intra;int *inter;} ptarr;
typedef struct {MPI_Comm intra_comm; MPI_Comm inter_comm;} gcom;
```

The interface for normal MPI_Alltoallv is:

```
int MPI_Alltoallv(void *bufin, int *scnt, int *sdpl, MPI_Datatype stype,
                 void *bufout, int *rcnt,int *rdpl, MPI_Datatype rtype, MPI_Comm comm)
```

In the following table we show the equivalent arguments in the same row and we also describe their differences:

MPI_Alltoallv (1)	MPI_Alltoallv_tuned (2)	Description
bufin / bufout	bufin / bufout	Input / output buffers. In case of (2) only double precision type is defined
scnt	gr_scnt	Integer array for (1). Data type ptarr for (2). ptarr has two integer arrays - inter and intra. inter part of ptarr contains counts for sending across nodes. The intra part of ptarr contains counts for sending within node.
sdpl	gr_sdpl	
rcnt	gr_rcnt	
rdpl	gr_rdpl	
comm	gcom	Data type MPI_Comm for (1). Data type gcom for (2). gcom has two parts intra and inter. intra part is communicator within node. inter part is the communicator across nodes.
stype, rtype	-	Data type MPI_Datatype for (1). Undefined for (2).

A typical usage scenario of MPI_Alltoallv_tuned is shown below:

```
step #1: MPI_Init
step #2: split MPI_COMM_WORLD
step #3: compute gr_xxx from xxx array
step #4: start do loop
step #5: MPI_Alltoallv_tuned
step #6: end do loop
```

Between steps #1 to #6 there can be other computational steps. The MPI_COMM_WORLD is split into intra and inter node communicator in #2. Then in step #3 gr_xxx is calculated from xxx arrays where xxx refers to scnt/ sdpl/ rcnt/ rdpl. These arguments are calculated outside MPI_Alltoallv_tuned routine. The calculation of gr_xxx from corresponding xxx array has some overhead. So we try to do it outside loops if the xxx array does not change in each of the iterations. The original code is changed in steps #2, #3 and #5.

2) Scope of this work

In the present work we are trying to make the interface of MPI_Alltoallv_tuned the same as MPI_Alltoallv. This will make it much easier to use in a real application. This means that steps #2 and #3 will be moved inside MPI_Alltoallv_tuned. However the calculation of gr_xxx from corresponding input array xxx is complicated and as stated before has some overhead including MPI exchanges. So we want to do it only once for a particular input array xxx. This can be achieved by internally storing a hash table of “key” - “value” pair for each array xxx. Where “key” is the cyclic redundancy check (CRC) checksum value of the input array and value is the array gr_xxx. For each invocation of MPI_Alltoallv_tuned the CRC “key” of an input array xxx will be calculated and matched with existing “keys” in the hash table. If there is a hit then the corresponding “value” in the hash table will be extracted and assigned to gr_xxx. If there is no hit gr_xxx will be calculated and then the new CRC “key” and corresponding gr_xxx “value” pair will be stored in the hash table. Fortunately in many MPI applications the send / receive counts do not change in every invocation. So for most invocations there will be a local hash table search to find the gr_xxx for the corresponding input xxx.

3) Results

We have used a 32-bit CRC algorithm (crc32) for finding checksum values of arrays. As the arrays concerned are integer arrays of the size of the number of MPI processes the upper limit of the array sizes will be of the order of 50000 or so. We think a 32 bit algorithm will be sufficient for such sizes. We have tested the uniqueness of the crc32 keys. For a large number of test cases we have randomly generated the integer arrays of various sizes and calculated its crc32 values. For all test cases crc32 keys are different if the arrays are different. So we can take the crc32 value as an unique id of an array. We have written functions to create, insert, search, extract hash table for arrays. In every invocation of MPI_Alltoallv_tuned there will be crc32 key calculation followed by hash table search. We have checked the overhead of these extra steps compared to actual data message send time which is shown in the table below.

ranks	Crc32 + hash table time [s]	MPI_Alltoallv time [s]
16	0.000002	0.000028
32	0.000004	0.000335
64	0.000006	0.001083
128	0.000009	0.005080
256	0.000016	0.019837
512	0.000041	0.096465
1024	0.000064	3.684677

As can be seen in the table above the overhead of key calculation and hash table search is very small compared to MPI_Alltoallv. The percentage overhead reduces with increasing number of ranks.

B. Increasing the parallelism in collective communication

1) The role of recent computer architectures for message passing

The main open-source MPI libraries as well as implementations by system vendors tailored for certain computer architectures must serve a broad spectrum of different application classes. They often are optimised to use the bandwidth of the interconnect network, while there is room for further optimisation in the communication with shorter, latency-bound messages. One example for this is the application NEK5000. [7] It contains an adaptable implementation of communication operations that are needed to implement its parallel direct solver for coarse grid problems. The communication module provides several algorithms of the communication functions. Amongst them are collective operations as they are provided by the MPI library of the respective platform as well as implementations using algorithms based on pairwise communication between MPI processes.

The specific properties of recent multi-core processor designs, the hardware support for multithreaded programming, and the availability of more powerful network interface cards allow to further improve collective operations by taking into account some of their characteristics. For example, each network interface chip on Cray systems is shared between two nodes and can work independently from the node CPUs. The chips have 10 network links that form a 3D-torus interconnect and incorporate a 48-port switch. This design allows several active networks connections at the same time as well as overlapping of communication and computation. [1]

Such technical features of hardware allow improvements of algorithms that have been designed in the past. For example, certain systems do not need to have only one network connection can be active at a certain point in time or communication and communication can be executed at the same time. We try to increase the number of messages travelling through the system in parallel as well as to use overlapping of communication and computation for collective operations. We look at broadcast and reduce operations as examples of this approach.

```

function broadcast(d, myrank, msg)
begin
  mask := 2d-1;
  for i := d-1 downto 0 do
    mask := mask xor 2i;
    if (myrank and mask) = 0 then
      if (myrank and 2i) == 0 then
        dest := myrank xor 2i;
        send msg to dest;
      else
        src := myrank xor 2i;
        receive msg from src;
      endif
    endif
  endfor
end

```

Figure 1. Broadcast communication in a hypercube network using blocking send and receive operations

```

function reduce(d, myrank, msg, m)
begin
  for j := 0 to m-1 do
    sum[j] := msg[j];
  mask := 0;
  for i := 0 to d-1 do
    if (myrank and mask) = 0 then
      peer := myrank xor 2i;
      if (myrank and 2i) ≠ 0 then
        dest := myrank xor 2i;
        send msg to peer;
      else
        receive msg from peer;
        reduce sum and msg;
      endif
    endif
    mask := mask xor 2i;
  endfor
end

```

Figure 3. Broadcast communication in a hypercube network using blocking send and receive operation.

```

function broadcast_o(d, myrank, msg, p)
begin
  open_send := 0;
  mask := 2d-1;
  for i := d-1 downto 0 do
    mask := mask xor 2i;
    if (myrank and mask) = 0 then
      if (myrank and 2i) == 0 then
        dest := myrank xor 2i;
        send_async msg to dest;
        open_send++;
        if open_send >= p then
          wait_for_all_sends;
          open_send := 0;
        endif
      else
        src := myrank xor 2i;
        receive msg from src;
      endif
    endif
  endfor
  if open_send >= p then
    wait_for_all_sends;
  endif
end

```

Figure 2. Broadcast communication in a hypercube network using up to p non-blocking send operations in one process at the same time.

```

function reduce_o(d, myrank, msg, m, s)
begin
  for j := 0 to m-1 do
    sum[j] := msg[j];
  mask := 0;
  for i := 1 to d-1 do
    if (myrank and mask) = 0 then
      peer := myrank xor 20;
      if (myrank and 2i) ≠ 0 then
        while not all_send(msg) do
          send part of msg to peer;
        else
          receive part of msg from peer;
          while not all_received(msg) do
            receive_async part of msg
              from peer;
            reduce part of sum and msg;
            wait_for_receive;
          endwhile
          reduce part of sum and msg;
        endif
      endif
    endif
  endfor
end

```

Figure 4. Reduce operation in a hypercube network using non-blocking receive operations

2) Examples for improved communication algorithms

The classical broadcast algorithm in a hypercube network has been described in [3] and is shown in fig. 1. Each bit position of a node label corresponds to one dimension of the hypercube. The communication starts at the highest dimension denoted with d . The message will be sent stepwise and successively along lower dimension. Each process but rank 0 receives the message once and sends it afterwards to the processes in the sub-cube defined by the bits of the remaining dimensions. This doubles the number of messages travelling through the system in parallel within each subsequent step.

The use of non-blocking send operations can help to improve the algorithm. It is shown in fig. 2. Each but rank 0 waits in a blocking receive operation for the message and starts after the receive a number of non-blocking send operations to its peers at lower dimensions. The allowed number of parallel send operations can be externally defined in order to adjust for the optimal node workload.

The classical reduce algorithm in a hypercube network has been described in [3] and is shown in fig. 3. It is the dual operation of the previously presented broadcast. The communication starts now at the lowest dimension. Each node sends its message to its neighbour in the current dimension. The receiving processes perform the reduction operation of incoming data with their own message and send the aggregated information subsequently to the peers in the next higher dimension. We see that each node receives and processes a number of messages that corresponds again to size of the sub-cube defined from the length of the sequence of continuous zeros in the rank starting at the lowest dimension. The number of messages travelling through the system in parallel is halved within each subsequent step.

Non-blocking communication can be used again in order to increase the number of messages travelling through the system in parallel. This approach would provide a similar communication speed like the dual broadcast operation. But, it would require to provide memory for multiple buffers in order to store incoming messages. Another option has been chosen here. Messages can be sent also in several packages using non-blocking communication. This allows to receive one part of the message and to perform the reduction operation for the part received previously in parallel. The algorithm is shown in fig. 4.

3) Results

The measurements have been done on a Cray XE6 system. The installation provides nodes with 32 GB RAM and 24 cores per node. The CPUs are AMD Magny Core processors with 12 cores and a clock frequency at 2.1 GHz. The interconnect network is based on Cray's Gemini technology. Each network interface chip is shared between two nodes and connected to other adapters by 10 links. One links allows an effective bandwidth of about 5GB per second in MPI. MPI has been used in its default configuration.

Figure 5. Broadcast 8192 ranks – wallclock time for different algorithms

Figure 6. Reduce 8192 ranks – wallclock time for different algorithms

Figure 7. Allreduce 8192 ranks – wallclock time for different algorithms

improvements even at longer message sizes. The performance of the broadcast operation could be increased up to 13 parallel communications for the used 8192 ($= 2^{13}$) processes. This indicates that it was not yet possible to saturate the network for this number of processes with short messages (fig. 5).

Reduce. Different implementations show the best results at different message lengths. Short messages are processed fastest with the hypercube-based algorithm using blocking communication. The hypercube algorithm that is based on non-blocking communication and message transfer in several parts provides for larger messages the highest performance (fig. 6).

Allreduce. Presently, the operation has been implemented as sequence of a reduce operation and a broadcast. The benchmarks confirmed as expected that this is not the best solution and the search for another algorithm is promising. The aggregated effect of both operations makes the hypercube algorithm based on non-blocking communication and message transfer in parts fastest for short messages, whereas the MPI function on the system is faster than both hypercube algorithms for larger message lengths (fig 7).

4) Discussion

The benchmark results point to the conditions, under which the alternative implementation of collective operation could be a promising activity. The MPI library provided on the platform provides superior performance at larger message lengths. An improvement for short messages could be achieved using point-to-point operations. The results let expect that further optimisations can be realised. The overlapping of communication and computation operations like in the reduce operation seems to be a very sensible mechanism that needs fine-tuning in order to become effective.

C. Automatic network topology identification

The collectives tuning outlined previously in this document critically depends on network topology, or at the very least on reliable mapping of MPI ranks to nodes, in order to utilise the higher bandwidth available for intra-node message passing. The automatic and unsupervised mapping of MPI ranks to individual nodes is the ultimate goal in the sub-task described in this section.

The order-of-magnitude difference in bandwidth and latency between intra node memory accesses and inter-node message passing, even over the fastest available interconnect, can serve as a basis for classification of rank-to-rank pair communications for an MPI based application as being either intra node or inter node. The rank pair mapping to identify individual nodes is then a matter of book keeping. Raw performance data which can be measured and potentially serve as a basis for this classification include:

- Bandwidth
- Small message latency
- Message rate

It is also plausible that derived data from the above, such as standard deviation of the gathered performance statistics could serve as a means for classification, since traversing an interconnect topology with switch and NUMA zone jumps will incur various overhead performance costs depending on how many layers must be traversed.

A number of methods from statistical modeling are available for unsupervised data cluster detection. Of primary interest here are:

- Hierarchical clustering models [13]
- K-means clustering [14]
- Statistical tree models [15]

The success of these methods in general depends on good separation of data into clusters and they typically can not handle complex or less well defined data clusters with any higher degree of fidelity.

Prototyping these classification schemes can be conveniently done using statistical programming tools such as R [18] which have a vast range of peer-reviewed statistical tools suitable for handling large data sets. R also has tools for scaling many computations appropriately, depending of data set size. Using R brings the added benefit that going from prototype R code to production level compiled code is facilitated by virtue of the open source nature of R, and its use of C, C++ and Fortran as implementation languages.

The goal of this study is a prototype implementation of an unsupervised classifier to identify groups of MPI ranks belonging to a specific node or possibly NUMA zone within a cluster or SMP machine.

1) Data clustering methods

Data clustering is a multivariate statistical method for finding structure in data. Finding structure in data is very easy, while finding generally valid and correct structure can be prohibitively difficult. Two methods in this area are of primary interest in this work, Hierarchical and K-means clustering. Highly interesting are also Tree models, or decision tree models, as they potentially offer a computationally cheap, simple, scalable and robust way to create a data classifier. Hierarchical clustering and K-means clustering are both examples of unsupervised clustering techniques, while tree models require input data, to be of use in this context and is not strictly a multivariate method in the same sense as the previous two methods.

Hierarchical clustering seeks to assign similarity between groups of samples by forming a similarity (or dissimilarity if you will) matrix consisting of euclidean distances in "data feature space". Other norms than the euclidean may be chosen. All samples are put in groups going from individual samples to a group containing all samples based on a similarity, forming a tree

like structure with the group containing all samples as the “root” of the tree structure and the leaves being the individual data samples.

Classical k-means clustering operates by assigning data samples to a specified number of centroids, multi-dimensional mean values, in the best possible manner by minimising the sum of squares of the euclidean distance to the centroid. The number of groups is user specified.

2) Initial results

The initial results presented here are based on bandwidth data obtained from the PRACE system Curie using eight of the “fat” nodes, the bullx S6010 model, with four 8-core Intel ® Nehalem-EX X7560 processors per node, connected by QDR Infiniband in full bisection. The data collection was done sending a series of 1 MB point-to-point messages between all rank pairs, timing the roundtrip time for the messages and reporting the average bandwidth and standard deviation of the samples. A total of 256 ranks and thereby 32640 unique rank pairs (a complete set) were used to collect this data.

As unsupervised data classification requires well separated data clusters to work, of central importance is the question of how well separated the data clusters are. Our initial findings based on bandwidth data suggests - as would be expected – that there are very good chances that the data clustering approach would work. The data clusters are plotted in figure 8.

The data gathered so far in this task is limited to bandwidth data and its associated standard deviation for a number of samplings (~20) of each rank pair. If standard deviation is to be used as a data classification variable the number of samples per rank pair needs to be increased to be statistically significant. As evident from figure 8, there is clearly good separation of data samples consistent between a) intra node, intra numa zone communications, 896 rank pairs, b) the highest bandwidth cluster intra node, inter numa zone communications, 3072 rank pairs in the medium bandwidth cluster, and c) the inter node communications in the low bandwidth cluster as would be expected with this type of compute nodes.

The only method of clustering investigated here so far is k-means clustering. How well does k-means clustering fare on these very well defined data clusters? The answer is: Not impressively well using an initial and naïve, out-of-the-box application of the k-means method on the raw data. Assigning the data to two clusters as illustrated in fig. 8b gives a reasonable partitioning which is completely successful separating intra node communication from inter-node communication. A three cluster identification which is simple to the human eye assigns two clusters to the low bandwidth cluster of figure 9, while keeping the two higher bandwidth clusters assigned as one single cluster. The situation continues when testing for four clusters, the lowest lying bandwidth cluster gets an additional split. It is not until the lowest bandwidth samples are disregarded when separate clusters can be assigned to the intra node rank pairs as shown in figure 8c, in the current data set.

3) Discussion

The failure of the naïve application of the k-means method can be attributed to two centroids being put in the lowest cluster as those sums of squares of data samples is lower than breaking up the two upper clusters in two. Clearly any use of the k-means method in this context will have to be a bit more sophisticated. Adding more data dimensions such as message rate and small message latency may help but is unlikely to be a sliver bullet.

It can be observed though, that if the objective is to only distinguish between intra and inter node communications, i.e. only two cluster assignments, then it is likely that the k-means method can do it even when applied as here. Going forward, it remains to be seen what can be achieved using more raw performance data, more refined modeling and other modeling types but

Figure 8. Scatterplots of round trip rank pair bandwidths in MB/s plotted against the standard deviation of the measurements in B/s. A: The complete data set of 32640 rank pairs. The top cluster consists of the 896 intra NUMA zone rank pairs. The mid bandwidth cluster consists of the 3072 inter NUMA zone, intra-node rank pairs. The low cluster consists of inter-node rank pairs communications. B: The two-cluster k-means assignment coded by red and blue dots. The blue dots represent intra node rank pairs. C: The two intra node communication categories as identified with the k-means method and removing inter node data.

it is clear that very well separated data can be obtained and the primary goal of this study – automatic and unsupervised distinguishing of intra node rank pairs from inter node rank pairs – has already been reached for this very limited data set.

Seeing the rank pair bandwidth data being as well separated as it is raises the question if straightforward sorting of rank pairs based on the bandwidth data and subsequent splits according to how many rank pair are intra-node intra-numazone and how many are intra-node inter-numazone is not a viable approach. After all, knowing the cluster node configuration in terms of socket count, CPU cores per socket and the total number of ranks (assuming one rank per core) will let us calculate in advance how many ranks there should be in each category. This will be fine for mapping ranks to nodes and NUMA zones but will by design not be able to detect topology on the interconnect fabric level. When topology detection on the fabric level is the objective, other approaches are necessary.

Considering the successful application of the hierarchical clustering sibling, neighbor joining as implemented by Subramoni et al. [17,18], the hierarchical clustering avenue of investigation will not be further pursued and attention instead turned

Figure 9. Cluster assignments of the sampled data using the *k*-means clustering method. Cluster assignments are displayed with different colors. Top left: Two clusters. Top right: Three clusters. Bottom left: Four clusters. Bottom right: Two clusters of the highest bandwidth data. Tree models seeks to find a generally valid “key” in terms of characteristic or distinguishing variable value ranges to a classification from a previously made classification. Depending on the quality of this key and the separation of data, it can form the basis of a very simple and computationally cheap classifier.

to tree models as they present an alternate approach, which offers simplicity of evaluation and embarrassingly parallel scaling. Using the current data, the tree model method of classification can be illustrated by the following pseudo code:

```
foreach rankpair {
  if (rankpair_bandwidth < 100_GB_per_second) {
    rankpair_category = internode
  } else if (rankpair_bandwidth > 2000_GB_per_second) {
    rankpair_category = intranode_intra_NUMAzone
  } else {
    rankpair_category = intranode_inter_NUMAzone
  }
}
```

Having a pre-defined set of feature characteristics, or a key, for classification of a rank pair will reduce the task of classification to a few operations per rank pair data point, which can be done by each rank independent of other ranks, i.e. an embarrassingly parallel task. Obviously this pre-defined key will need to be generated on a system-by-system basis. The classification key is not limited to bandwidth data and can also be used for instance with latency or message rate information.

Given the preliminary nature of the data presented here, especially as the k-means method track will be discontinued, no measure of the correctness of the clusters detected have been made which is otherwise standard practise.

IV. FURTHER WORK

The integration of all the steps described above into `MPI_Alltoally_tuned_new` is ongoing. Once this integration is done we will try to use this routine in some community code, e.g., which uses all-to-all communication heavily.

The current results show the potential for the improvement of latency-bound communication operations and motivate further work. Collective algorithms will be extended and further optimised. More possibilities for optimisation besides the use of non-blocking communication will be incorporated into the implementation. This includes the exploitation of shared memory for multi-core CPUs and multi-socket nodes as well as to consider the interconnect topology.

Topology detection in an automated fashion can clearly be done based on statistical tools analysing rank-to-rank communication performance as evidenced by data obtained here and implementations presented in recent publications by Subramoni et al [16, 17]. To provide an alternative to the very successful methodology presented by them, future work will focus on Tree models classification and the very attractive scaling characteristics they could offer and their inherent simplicity.

V. LITERATURE

- [1] Alverson, R.; Roweth, D.; Kaplan, L.; , "The Gemini System Interconnect," High Performance Interconnects (HOTI), 2010 IEEE 18th Annual Symposium on , vol., no., pp.83-87, 18-20 Aug. 2010
- [2] Edgar Gabriel, Saber Feki, Katharina Benkert, and Michael M. Resch, 'Towards Performance and Portability through Runtime Adaption for High Performance Computing Applications', in 'Concurrency and Computation - Practice and Experience', vol. 22, no. 16, pp. 2230-2246, 2010.
- [3] Ananth Grama, Anshul Gupta, George Karypis and Vipin Kumar. Introduction to Parallel Computing. 2nd edition. Harlow, London, New York,....: Pearson, 2003.
- [4] Teng Ma; Heralut, T.; Bosilca, G.; Dongarra, J.J.; , "Process Distance-Aware Adaptive MPI Collective Communications," IEEE International Conference on CLuster Computing (CLUSTER) 2011, pp.196-204, 26-30 Sept. 2011.
- [5] Michael Schliephake, Xavier Aguilar, Erwin Laure: Design and Implementation of a Runtime System for Parallel Numerical Simulations on Large-Scale Clusters. *Procedia Computer Science*, Volume 4, Proceedings of the International Conference on Computational Science, ICCS 2011, 2105-2114, 2011.
- [6] Bibo Tu, Jianping Fan, Jianfeng Zhan, Xiaofang Zhao. Performance analysis and optimization of MPI collective operations on multi-core clusters. *The Journal of Supercomputing*. V 60 (2012) 1. pp. 141-162.
- [7] H. M. Tufo and P. F. Fischer, "Terascale Spectral Element Algorithms and Implementations" Gordon Bell Prize paper, Proc. of the ACM/IEEE SC99 Conf. on High Performance Networking and Computing. IEEE Computer Soc., CDROM (1999).
- [8] Michael Schliephake, Erwin Laure: Communication Performance Analysis of CRESTA's Co-Design Application NEK5000. Workshop *Preparing Applications for Exascale Through Co-design* in *International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, SC '12*. Salt Lake City, November 10-16, 2012.
- [9] Improving MPI communication latency of Euroben kernels, Chandan Basu. National Supercomputer Center, Linköping University, Linköping, 581 83, Sweden, http://www.prace-ri.eu/IMG/pdf/improving_mpi_communication_latency_on_euroben_kernels.pdf
- [10] Home page of the EuroBen Benchmark. <http://www.hpcresearch.nl/euroben/index.php>
- [11] M. J. Rashti, J. Green, P. Balaji , A. Afsahi and W. Gropp, Multi-core and Network Aware MPI Topology Functions, EuroMPI'11 Proceedings of the 18th European MPI Users' Group conference on Recent advances in the message passing interface , Pages 50-60.
- [12] T. Ma, G. Bosilca, A. Bouteiller and J. J. Dongarra, Locality and Topology aware Intra-node Communication Among Multicore CPUs, Proceeding EuroMPI'10 Proceedings of the 17th European MPI users' group meeting conference on Recent advances in the message passing interface Pages 265-27.
- [13] K. Kandalla, H. Subramoni, A. Vishnu and D. K. Panda, Designing Topology-Aware Collective Communication Algorithms for Large Scale InfiniBand Clusters:Case Studies with Scatter and Gather, Parallel & Distributed Processing, Workshops and Phd Forum (IPDPSW), 2010 IEEE International Symposium, 19-23 April 2010, Pages 1 – 8
- [14] Gordon A. D., "A review of hierarchical classification", *Journal of the Royal Statistical Soc. A*, **150**, pp. 119-137
- [15] Ball G. H. and Hall D. J., "A clustering technique for summarizing multivariate data", *Behavioural Science*, **12**, pp. 153 – 155
- [16] Breiman, L.; Friedman, J. H.; Olshen, R. A. and Stone, C. J., "Classification and regression trees". Monterey, CA: Wadsworth & Brooks/Cole Advanced Books & Software, 1984

- [17] Subramoni, H.; Potluri, S.; Kandalla, K.; Barth, B.; Vienne, J.; Keasler, J.; Tomko, K.; Schulz, K.; Moody, A. and Panda, D. K., “Design of a scalable InfiniBand topology service to enable network-topology-aware placement of processes” Proc. of the International Conference on High Performance Computing, Networking, Storage and Analysis, IEEE Computer Soc., pp. 70:1—70:12
- [18] H. Subramoni; K. Kandalla; J. Vienne; S. Sur; B. Barth; K. Tomko; R. McLay; K. Schulz; and D. K. Panda, “Design and Evaluation of Network Topology-/Speed- Aware Broadcast Algorithms for InfiniBand Clusters”, IEEE International Conference on Cluster Computing (CLUSTER) 2011, pp. 317 – 325, 26-30 Sept. 2011.
- [19] R Development Core Team (2008). R: A language and environment for statistical computing. R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria. ISBN 3-900051-07-0, URL <http://www.R-project.org>.